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Influence of Parental Child Rearing Techniques on the Academic Performance of Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of parental child rearing techniques on the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. To achieve the purpose of the study, the researcher developed four objectives of the study, four research questions and four hypotheses that guided the conduct of the study. The research design used for the study was a descriptive survey design. The population of the study consisted of all the teachers in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State with a population size of 2,018 teachers. Simple random sampling technique was used with a sample size of 400 teachers. The instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled “Influence of Parental Child Rearing Techniques on the Academic Performance Questionnaire”. The instrument was rated using four point rating scale. The data collected was analyzed using frequency table and weighted mean score for the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistical tool at a significant level of 0.05. Based on the data analysis, the finding of the study revealed that authoritarian, permissive, and authoritative child rearing patterns have positive and significant effect on student’s academic performance. Based on the findings, the study recommends that: government should organize awareness campaign on the right parenting pattern to use, parents should keep the right relationship with their family for their children upbringing and parents should avoid uninvolved/neglectful child rearing pattern hence it affects the students negatively in their academic performance.

Keywords: Authoritarian, Authoritative, Child Rearing, Permissive, Influence, Parental, Techniques

INTRODUCTION

Parents play a highly influential role in their children’s development. Baumrind (2022) in his study identifies that pre-school children raised by parents with differing parenting styles varied in their degree of social competence. Parenting styles can be categorized according to the levels of parental demandingness i.e. control, supervision and maturity demands and responsiveness i.e. warmth, acceptance and involvement (Maccoby and Martin, 2013). Parenting styles have often been presented as a three-category structure which is; authoritarian, authoritative and permissive parenting styles. An

authoritarian parent demands obedience from the child and tries to shape and control the child's behaviours with an absolute set of standards. In contrast, a permissive parent tends to offer as much freedom as the child wants, not demanding any form of conformity as long as the child's physical safety is not at risk. An authoritative parent, on the other hand, values both the child's autonomy and open communication with the child. An authoritative parent enforces rules and standards using commands and sanctions when necessary. Wentzel (2019) notes that we have authoritative, neglected or uninvolved, authoritarian and permissive child rearing patterns.

One important art to learn by children in the course of their interaction with adults is the art of studying. The child needs an enabling environment in order to develop good study habits. Put more succinctly, the child-rearing pattern of the parents would be seen to be an important factor in achieving good study habits. This position is yet to be proved beyond reasonable doubts. In contribution, Way and Robert (2015) opine along the above background that parent-child relationship or relatedness facilitates risk taking, learning and exploration, which are building blocks for ego identify formation. Parental child rearing practices are all the patterns or methods that parents employ in the process of taking care of their children. In line with this view, Shafter (2018) identifies parenting styles as authoritative, authoritarian and permissive. Authoritative parenting model is a more flexible form of parenting where considerable freedom is given to children yet restriction is imposed upon them but satisfying reasons are given for the restriction imposed.

Authoritarian parenting is also known as autocratic and rigid form of parenting. McAdam (2014) posits that strict rules are given and enforced as if they were divine edicts in authoritarian parenting. Permissive parenting is that form of parenting model which allows the child to disregard parental wishes. This also sums up the classification identified by Iwundu (2015). He believes that these three models are the various ways parents interact with their children more than any other agents of socialization. The parents at the child's early stage in life act upon the character of their children. The development of negative identity in adolescence is part of the parental style the child received at early stage in life which Steinberge (2019) sees as selecting of identity undesirable to community.

The choice of a negative identity formation will not be the aim of any parent to the child, but the child out of parental style he finds himself can choose his own way after all, being bad as better than not knowing what one really is. This becomes the manner in which such child finds negative identity desirable reasons. Against the above backdrops, one can deduce that the interaction or relationship between the child and the parents bring about character formation in the child.

Conceptual Review

Parental Child Rearing Practices

Parental child rearing practice is an umbrella word that goes on to tell about all forms of parental involvement with children and the kind of relationship, which exist between them. It determines how a child develops. Parenting is a task that requires mastery to attain, good result. Rice (2013) believes that for some people, living childless even with a loving mate is unthinkable and that couples need to give considerable thoughts to the responsibilities involved in bringing up children. Dail and Way in Rice (2013) opined that child rearing philosophies change from one generation to the next and that parents often have to sort out conflicting advice. This indicates that parents are sometimes torn between decisions on how best to bring up 'their children as a lot of advice and opinions are open to them. The researcher, wish to stand out to investigate and bring to view a standpoint for parents on how to bring up their children.

Walter and Walter (2020) noted that what is important is the quality of the child-parent relationship and the total climate of the family setting rather than the philosophy of child rearing that is followed, looking at this closely, they view the child differences (individual differences) and suggest that the style good for one may not be the best for another. Others have observed that for adolescents, the single most important external inference to accomplish the developmental task is his parents. Parents are important in preparing one adolescent to meet up the unpredictable world of tomorrow since they act as both models and

nurturers of their adolescents which means parenting styles affect adolescent. These parental reactions had. been identified as affecting the adolescence developmental process; they are: parental love or rejection, calm or anxious, involved or uninvolved, rigid or flexible, controlling or permissive Two terms deduced from the aforementioned characteristics has been identified as demandingness and responsiveness (Baumrind, 2018).

Parental Patterns or Styles

Parental attitudes and behaviours that are performed while raising children have a significant impact on children's future behaviour as well as shaping behaviour at early ages. Children must have healthy relationships with their parents in order to display consistent behaviours in society, to be self-sufficient, to gain necessary social skills, and achieve his/her independence. This is closely related with parental attitudes and behaviours; i.e. the parenting styles that the parents adopt. The most common parental attitudes are classified as authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, uninvolved and overprotective (Baumrind 2021).

With democratic parents, not only are children supervised, but there is a sensibility to their immediate needs as well. Parents are immensely sensitive, consistent, decisive, permissive, reassuring and supportive to children. These parents encourage their children to be independent while they keep controlling the actions of their children. Despite the fact that the final responsibility lays with the parent, the children are also consulted in these families. Therefore, the children believe that their views are also important. It is probable that children with democratic parents are social, autonomous and highly responsible (Baumrind, 2021).

Authoritarian parents display little warmth and a high degree of control. They are strict disciplinarians and use a punitive and restrictive style. Authoritarian parents expect their children to obey rules and instructions set by them without questioning. Authoritarian parents may use expressions such as "You will do that, because I say so". These behaviours may cause the adolescent to be dependent and rebellious. Rebellious adolescents display aggressive behaviours, whereas obedient/submissive adolescents can be dependent on their families (Baumrind, 2021).

Permissive parents display a high degree of warmth, but they are undemanding and do not have high expectations. According to this permissive and passive parenting style, the only way to show love to adolescents is to indulge all their wishes. Expressions such as, "Of course you can stay out late if you want" may be used by these parents. Permissive parents do not want to cause disappointment by saying no. Therefore, adolescents may make many decisions independently from their parents. This situation may cause difficulties for the adolescents in controlling themselves and may result in tendencies to display egocentric behaviours (Baumrind, 2021). The permissive and loose attitudes of the parents cause children to be spoiled and expect that they will be given priority over the other individuals in the society. When they are not given priority, the individuals feel restless and uncomfortable and cannot adapt to social relationships outside the family.

Alternatively, other parents who have the same goal may institute strict rules of what can and cannot be consumed in the family home. What spells the difference between these two alternatives has been understood as the parenting style of the parents. Child (2018) suggests that parenting style is an emotional climate in the home where the children are situated. Based on their research, there are three dimensions that influence parental success in terms of raising their children, though they were not outlined explicitly, but simply mentioned throughout the study: responsiveness (versus unresponsiveness), demanding (versus undemanding), and autonomy granting. All three dimensions have been determined to have a relationship to child outcomes.

Three parenting styles conceptualized and developed throughout the years by Baumrind (2021), with the addition made by Nei (2013) of the neglectful parenting style, comprise the current scholarly understanding of parenting styles as a typology that encompasses a variety of parental behaviors. To summarize, there are four parenting styles: authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and neglectful or uninvolved. The distinctions between them can be measured in the respective levels they have on two

primary features of parenting: responsiveness and demandingness. Responsiveness is “often operationalized using measures of parental warmth and acceptance, while demandingness came to be defined with respect to parental firmness”

The authoritative parenting style exhibits high levels of responsiveness and demandingness (Uba, 2017). The authoritarian parenting style exhibits a low level of responsiveness but a high level of demandingness. The permissive parenting style exhibits a high level of responsiveness but a low level of demandingness. The neglectful parenting style exhibits low levels of responsiveness and demandingness. It must be noted that, while numerous studies have been conducted among European-Americans that revealed the superiority of the authoritative parenting style over other parenting styles, and its benefits on children in terms of their life outcomes, even across different age groups noted that possible divergences may emerge in what contribute significantly toward positive outcomes among children, depending on the cultural group studied.

Parenting patterns are beneficial in understanding complex behaviour and attitudes associated with child outcomes. Parenting is parental behaviours which encompass pleasures, privileges and profits as well as frustrations, fears, and failures. Thus, parents can find an interest and derive considerable and continuing pleasure in their relationships and activities with their children (Dawkins, 2016).

It is generally agreed that parenting style influences self-efficacy, self-esteem, and identity development, which are associated with academic achievement (Brown and Iyengar, 2018). In addition, the progress in children’s achievement is influenced by the decision that is made by both parents and their children to cooperate or confront each other. Furthermore, children’s academic motivation and behavior are directly influenced by family activities and parents’ behavior, which are seen as the external factor. For instance, there is a positive outcome for both parents and children when parents interact in a fun and loving way during children’s homework time (Morawska, 2017).

Conversely, when parents are neglectful, academic disengagement and problem behavior are generated. One study found that mothers who were better to modulate emotion and ability to both intimacy and autonomy had children who had higher scores for verbal and math achievement (Skowron, 2015). Further, parents are seen to communicate their characteristics or explanations for their children’s achievement in terms of day-to-day interactions and behavior with their children. Therefore, parents are influenced by their children’s academic achievement, and children’s achievement is, in turn, influenced by their parents.

Whether parents practice democratic decision making with their children; which can be defined as engagement in cooperative discussion prior to decision making is a criterion that is commonly used to measure parenting style. Authoritative parents tend to engage in discussions with their child before a more or less joint decision is rendered. Authoritarian and permissive parents, however, tend not to engage in discussions. Instead, unilateral decisions are the norm, with authoritarian parents and children of permissive parents making the decisions. However, most families are not completely democratic or undemocratic decision makers. Thus, this dimension is best measured as a continuum of authoritativeness (Morawska, 2017).

The Authoritarian Parenting Pattern: This parenting style is distinguished primarily by its high level of demandingness or control and its low level of responsiveness or warmth. A hallmark of the authoritarian parenting style is the imposition of a familial context that limits the independence of children through the establishment of rigid rules and standards regarding their behavior, maintained by strictly enforcing punitive measures (such as a withholding of allowance or other benefits and “grounding”) for violations (Uba, 2017). Inflexible limits are placed by authoritarian parents on their children and open discussions regarding those limits are rarely allowed. Questioning adults are strongly discouraged in the children of authoritarian parents; children who argue with them are dismissed by frequently telling that they will understand their parental decisions once they become parents themselves (Nei, 2013). Children who grow up under authoritarian parents could become accustomed to being dependent on their parents to make decisions, leading to a higher likelihood for negative outcomes once they grow older and have to make decisions for themselves.

As a result, children who grow up under authoritarian parents exhibit higher rates of low self-esteem, social incompetence (Baumrind, 2021), and child psychopathology. Moreover, the authoritarian parenting style, often utilized by parents who strongly desire for their children to make the correct decisions in life, has paradoxically been found to be, at best, ineffective in dissuading high-risk behaviors, especially during the crucial juncture of adolescence, such as unhealthy eating habits. Adolescents who come from authoritarian families tend to be more hostile and defensive, more prone to emotional outbursts and mood swings, and are more likely to harbor a negative worldview.

The authors found a notable negative relationship amongst the participants' experiences of an authoritarian parenting style and their home, health, and emotional adjustment in adolescence. They claimed that children who come from authoritarian homes experience heightened levels of chronic stress, which they try to overcome or alleviate through an indulgence in high-risk behaviors, such as alcohol or drug abuse. The authoritative parenting style determined to have a significant favorable correlation to the home, health, and emotional adjustment of the adolescents studied.

However, as the authors themselves noted, the results they obtained in their study may be influenced in unclear ways by the cultural context in which it was conducted (Uba, 2017). The consideration of cultural context as a possible influence on the merits of different parenting styles may require the use of a qualitative research method to gather in-depth data on this topic with regard to the essence of the problem and the many facets and features that need to be understood. A recommendation was also made to study a larger sample of students from different cultural backgrounds to provide a greater comprehensive picture of parenting styles and its influence on children's results in life.

Carmen (2016) explained that studying the effects of parenting styles in different societies could lead to different results due to the variance of how they construe specific concepts. For instance, the country of Spain, described as horizontal collectivistic, emphasizes the benefits of egalitarian relations rather than hierarchical relations; this meant that strictness "would not retain the positive meaning that it has in other cultural contexts, such as the United States (described as vertical individualistic) or in Asia (described as vertical collectivistic). While this explanation continues to be open for contention among scholars, theoretical and empirical studies conducted among cultural groups other than European-Americans have yielded information that has lent support to the relative nature of parenting styles. An example would be the placing of less emphasis on individual inherent ability with regard to academic achievement in Asian countries, compared to Western countries (Okon, 2019).

Scholarly support for the negative influence of the authoritarian parenting style on the results of young people have been strong. However, as has been noted previously, a large amount of the research that was conducted on this topic focused on European-American parents and children, which may be a significant factor in the kind of results that have been obtained. Empirical studies on Chinese-American families, for instance, disclosed the authoritarian parenting style might lead to affirmative outcomes for their children (Okon, 2019).

The authoritarian parenting style is the most common dysfunctional parenting style and has been found to have the most likelihood to contribute toward negative outcomes for children (Okon, 2019). However, the negative effects of the permissive parenting style have been noted as well, though not as often studied. The studies conducted on the permissive parenting style have tended to yield inconclusive results, though some reveal unequivocally negative outcomes for children. Carrera (2022) conducted a study to determine whether a connection existed amongst parental feeding practices and the particular parenting style utilized.

The permissive parenting style: Bissell (2020) suggest that the permissive parenting style is characterized by its high levels of responsiveness, warmth, or acceptance and low levels of demandingness. Children of parents that display a permissive parenting style are provided minimal standards or controls imposed upon them, and very few demands, if any, are made of them. "Along with the authoritarian parenting style, the permissive parenting style is generally understood as dysfunctional", in comparison to the authoritative parenting style, which is generally understood as optimal. A number of difficulties arise in children who come from permissive homes, as identified by researchers. As revealed in children of authoritarian parents,

the extremely elevated levels of control have shown to relate to increased rates of undesirable outcomes: unhealthy eating habits.

Conversely, it would be reasonable to assume that extremely low levels of control could also lead to negative outcomes. It is possible that the factor that most strongly contributes toward negative outcomes for children is not the kind of responsiveness paid by their parents, but rather the degree of responsiveness. At the very least, the correlation between permissive parenting and negative outcomes for children must be studied, as this dysfunctional parenting style has largely been ignored compared to the authoritarian parenting style (Uba, 2017).

Generally, permissive child rearing style allows the adolescent to disregard: parental wishes (Elder, 2020). Their parents may neglect their behaviour towards them and towards others. They are allowed to do whatever they demand and whatever came to their mind. This behaviour prevails probably because their parents fail to provide the kind of support the adolescent needs. Such parents find it difficult to make decisive value judgments that require the exercise of power over their children and prefer to escape from the obligation of being an authority figure”.

Different kinds of permissive parenting produce different adolescents;

- i. **Permissive Indulgent:** These are parents who are undemanding but highly responsive. They exercise little control over their children and are loving. They behave in an accepting, benign and passive way in matters of discipline, placing few demands on child's behaviour, giving then a high degree of freedom to act according to their wishes. Their belief is likely that control over children is an infringement on the child's right and could interfere with healthy development, they tend to look out to themselves as resources that the child could use or not (Steinberg, 2019).
- ii. **Permissive Indifferent:** In extreme cases, they may be neglectful, know little about what the activities of their children are and their where about, show little interest in their child's activities in school and with friends. They are mainly parents centered, thinking about themselves alone, preoccupying themselves with their needs instead of having anytime to talk about their child. One characteristic of children here is that they show the highest level of problem behaviour and internalized distress such as depression Steinberg (2019). He continues to observe that adolescent raised in indifferent home are often Impulsive, and more likely to incline to experiment with sex, drugs and alcohol.

The Uninvolved or Neglectful Parenting Pattern: This parenting style is characterized primarily by its low levels of both responsiveness and demandingness. This is also known as neglectful parenting style. It is easy to integrate with the permissive parenting style at first glance. The key difference is that while they both ask very little of their children in terms of standards, permissive parents respond to their children, although often their peers or friends, and not optimally, as parents with authority. Neglectful parents, similar to permissive parenting style, the neglectful parenting style has been connected to the increased likelihood of negative outcomes for children by scholars. This is due to its lack of clear, established standards and rules, effectively leaving children to make decisions for themselves without the knowledge and experience to do so.

Children with neglectful mothers ate fruits and vegetables less often, which may affect their long-term health outcomes negatively. However, given that it was a cross-sectional study, causality between the variables of parenting style and nutritional intake cannot be expressed with certainty. Fathers were also not involved in the study, which may have influenced the results. The cross-sectional and longitudinal association between parenting styles and female delinquency utilizing a sample of 330 Dutch families with a child from ages 14-22 was examined by Miller (2020). Differences based on sex were found in the study. The use of a neglectful parenting style was determined to be related to increased amounts of delinquency amongst male children, while the use of a permissive parenting style was found to relate to increased levels of delinquency among female children. The negative effects of a neglectful parenting style are strengthened when both parents share the same style.

The Authoritative Parenting Styles: This style of parenting is characterized by its high levels of both responsiveness and demandingness. The support for this parenting style in the literature has consistently been robust throughout the years, both in theoretical and empirical research (Baumrind, 2021). The benefits of this parenting style have been identified by scholars working in diverse fields, such as psychology, nutrition, and social work. An overwhelming amount of the research conducted on the topic of parenting style has generally determined its positive influence on the life outcomes of children, in various life dimensions such as health, social adjustment, and academic success. Despite the robust nature of the support for this parenting style, a number of scholars have identified the need for further research on this topic, given the differences among cultural groups in perceiving parenting styles. If culture influences what people perceive as effective parenting, then it would seem to follow that differences in culture may lead to differences in effective parenting styles.

The authoritative parenting style was linked to a higher quality of adhesiveness to the treatment regimen in relation to other parenting styles. The permissive parenting style specifically mentioned as a factor that predicted poor adherence to the treatment regimen. This is different to the authoritarian parenting style, which was “not associated with either glycemic control or treatment adherence” (Blum, 2016). It is noteworthy that, in some cases, the permissive parenting style can in fact be more detrimental to children compared to the authoritarian parenting style. Other negative results have also been found to be connected to the permissive parenting style. Despite a study from the same authors revealing children of parents that demonstrate a permissive parenting style are more likely to engage in physical activity, which was explained as the likely result if children are left unsupervised to devise ways to spend their time independently, this positive outcome may be counteracted by other behaviors that arise from the same factors. For instance, high levels of television watching in children have long been seen to correlate with a number of health risks, such as too much sedentary time and a predilection toward unhealthful food (junk food), both of which contribute toward obesity.

Statement of the Problem

It can be noted that in the district, the performance of students in schools is not that up-to-standards. This is where only a few of the students from this area receive the opportunity to further their education in the higher institutions of learning. Moreover, there are a number of more recent studies which have indicated that the performance of students in the study area have not been that impressive. However, none has been able to investigate how exactly the parental characteristics affect the performance of students. A person’s upbringing has a profound influence on how they see the world and how they process information. It was also observed that different students view education as having different goals.

Recent developments in the field of parenting and family studies have led to the renewed interest in the relationship between children’s school performance and child rearing patterns. These developments have heightened the need for the study on children’s school achievements. Since the family is the first window of the child, parenting style and its influence on children could greatly affect their understanding, attitude and school performance. Accordingly, there are several research works done on parent-child relationship and children’s school performance and behaviors that are required for a successful adaptation to the society and the family.

Some researchers have observed unique situations where secondary school learners from some family backgrounds attain significantly high grades than others. Child rearing is an important responsibility in every family. The child is a product of what his family is. Different parental child rearing practices may likely produce different kinds of individuals. It is observed that some children no longer live completely on parental values and ideas’ as he interacts and picks up some from his peers in school and also as he exercises his independent thinking. The way a child is brought up has influence on his or her study habits in secondary schools. But the degree of such an influence is not yet known especially among secondary school students in Port Harcourt.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the influence of parental child rearing techniques on the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The objectives among others bordered on the need to:

1. Examine the extent authoritarian child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
2. Investigate the extent permissive child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
3. Determine the extent authoritative child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
4. Examine the extent uninvolved child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Research Questions

The researcher developed the following research questions that guided study:

1. To what extent does authoritarian child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis?
2. To what extent does permissive child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis?
3. To what extent does authoritative child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis?
4. To what extent does uninvolved child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided this study.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on the extent authoritarian child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on the extent permissive child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on the extent authoritative child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
4. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on the extent uninvolved child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey design. This design is considered most suitable because it gives the researcher the confidence to attribute all the observed differences between the independent and dependent variables. The population of the study consisted of all the teachers in all the public Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt City and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area. The total population size is two thousand and eighteen (2,018) teachers. (Source: Ministry of Education, 2022). The sampling technique that was used for the study is simple random sampling technique. This was drawn by slips of papers. Out of 36 public secondary schools in the study area, all the teachers in the selected schools were administered with the instruments. However, the sample size of the study was four hundred (400) teachers. This was 19.8% of the total population. This figure was drawn using Taro Yamane formula. Therefore, we have 150 male respondents and 250 female respondents. The instrument that was used for data collection in the study was structured questionnaire titled: "Influence of Parental Child Rearing Techniques on the Academic Performance Questionnaire". It is patterned toward modified 4-point scale of Very High Extent (VHE),

High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). The instrument that was used in this study was validated using the researcher’s supervisor and three other experts in Measurement and Evaluation and Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling, Faculty of Education, Rivers State University. To ensure the reliability of the study, the researcher adopted test-retest method. The instrument was administered to twenty (30) secondary school teachers in Emohua Local Government Area who were not part of the study respondents for two (2) consecutive times within three (3) weeks interval. The two measures were compared using the Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient and a reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the null hypotheses were tested using t-transformation at 0.05 level of significance with a critical value of +1.96 when the calculated t-value was less than the critical value of +1.96, the null hypotheses was accepted and rejected` when the calculated t-value was greater than t-critical value of +1.96

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent does authoritarian child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 1: Mean Responses on the extent authoritarian child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students

S/ N	Questionnaire Items	Male (\bar{X})	SD	Decisio n	Female (\bar{X})	SD	Decisio n
1.	Some parental way of life imposes restrictions which affect the child’s academic performance in secondary school.	3.1 7	0.7 8	High Extent	3.18	0.7 1	High Extent
2.	Parents in autocratic child rearing pattern are responsive to their children’s needs and their point of view.	3.1 4	0.8 0	High Extent	3.35	0.7 3	High Extent
3.	Strict rules are given and enforced by parents in autocratic child rearing pattern which may affect the students’ academic performance	3.2 1	0.7 9	High Extent	3.29	0.7 3	High Extent
4.	Children from autocratic parenting family are obedient, conforming and academic competent.	3.2 2	0.7 3	High Extent	3.33	0.6 7	High Extent
5.	Being fearful, irritable, easily annoyed, passively hostile is some of the qualities of autocratic parenting style.	3.1 9	0.7 5	High Extent	3.28	0.7 3	High Extent
Grand Total		3.19	0.77		3.29	0.75	

Source: Field Survey 2024

Table 1 above reveals that the respondents accepted the view that some parental way of life imposes restrictions which affect the child’s s academic performance in secondary school. They also accepted the point that parents in autocratic child rearing pattern are responsive to their children’s needs and their point of view. It was also observed from the reveal that the respondents accepted the fact that strict rules are given and enforced by parents in autocratic child rearing pattern which may affects the students’ academic performance. The analysis also indicates that the respondents accepted that children from autocratic parenting family are obedient, conforming and academic competent. It still shows that the respondents accepted that being fearful, irritable, easily annoyed, passively hostile is some of the qualities of autocratic parenting style.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does permissive child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 2: Mean Responses on the extent permissive child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis

S/ N	Questionnaire Items	Male (\bar{X})	SD	Decision	Female (\bar{X})	SD	Decision
6.	Parents not having adequate control or regulation of their children affect their academic performance	3.88	0.94	High Extent	3.27	0.75	High Extent
7.	Children from permissive parental home exhibit worse impulse control thereby affecting their academic performance.	2.84	0.89	High Extent	3.21	0.74	High Extent
8.	Children from permissive parental home have more behavioural problem which affect their academic performance	3.19	0.79	High Extent	2.19	0.72	High Extent
9.	Democratic parenting styles relate to students study habits in secondary schools.	3.19	0.77	High Extent	3.18	0.78	High Extent
10.	Children from permissive parental home have low motivation thereby affecting their academic performance.	3.24	0.81	High Extent	2.25	0.74	High Extent
Grand Total		2.67	0.84		3.22	0.74	

Source: Field Survey 2024

Table 2 above indicates that the respondents accepted the view that parents not having adequate control or regulation of their children affect their academic performance. The analysis also shows that the respondents accepted the point that children from permissive parental home exhibit worse impulse control thereby affecting their academic performance. It was still observed from the study that the respondents accepted the fact that children from permissive parental home have more behavioural problem which affect their academic performance. The respondents also accepted the view that democratic parenting styles relate to students' study habits in secondary schools. The analysis still reveals that the respondents accepted the point that children from permissive parental home have low motivation thereby affecting their academic performance.

Research Question 3: *To what extent does authoritative child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 3: Mean Responses on the extent authoritative child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Male (\bar{X})	SD	Decision	Female (\bar{X})	SD	Decision
11.	Authoritative parenting style promotes students' academic performance in secondary school.	3.21	.793	High Extent	3.24	.764	High Extent
12.	Authoritative parenting style promotes students' self-efficacy thereby enhancing their academic performance.	3.09	.838	High Extent	3.18	.770	High Extent
13.	Students from authoritative parenting home have mastery goal behaviour like independence which enhance their academic performance.	3.26	.725	High Extent	3.20	.759	High Extent
14.	Authoritative parenting style raised the confidence of their children thereby enhancing their academic performance.	3.28	.752	High Extent	3.26	.718	High Extent
15.	Better social styles and pitiable problem –solving enhance students' academic performance.	3.26	.738	High Extent	3.06	.818	High Extent
Grand Total		3.22	0.77		3.19	0.77	

Source: Field Survey 2024

Table 3 above shows that the respondents accepted the fact that authoritative parenting style promotes students' academic performance in secondary school. The analysis also indicates that the respondents accepted the point that authoritative parenting style promotes students' self-efficacy thereby enhancing their academic performance. It was still observed from the study that the respondents accepted the view that students from authoritative parenting home have mastery goal behaviour like independence which enhance their academic performance. The analysis still shows that the respondents accepted the fact that authoritative parenting style raised the confidence of their children thereby enhancing their academic performance. The study also shows that the respondents accepted the point that better social styles and pitiable problem solving enhance students' academic performance.

Research Question 4: *To what extent does uninvolved child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 4: Mean Responses on the extent uninvolved child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis

S/ N	Questionnaire Items	Male (\bar{X})	SD	Decision	Female (\bar{X})	SD	Decision
16.	Parents having minimum interference in their children affect their academic performance	3.30	0.757	High Extent	3.29	0.73	High Extent
17.	Parental practice of allowing children to act or behave how they want affects their academic performance.	3.34	0.724	High Extent	3.34	0.71	High Extent
18.	Parental little or no inter reference or regulation affect their academic performance.	3.58	0.792	High Extent	3.30	0.75	High Extent
19.	Laissez-faire parental pattern leads to the lowest productivity among the students.	3.16	0.765	High Extent	3.27	0.74	High Extent
20.	Uninvolved relates to students' academic performance in public secondary schools.	3.22	0.768	High Extent	3.14	0.79	High Extent
Grand Total		2.92	0.76		3.27	0.74	

Source: Field Survey 2024

Table 4 above reveals that the respondents accepted the view that parents having minimum interference in their children affect their academic performance. They also accepted the point that Parental practice of allowing children to act or behave how they want affects their academic performance. It was also observed from the study that the respondents accepted the fact that parental little or no inter reference or regulation affect their academic performance. The analysis also indicates that the respondents accepted that laissez-faire parental pattern leads to the lowest productivity among the students. It still shows that the respondents accepted that laissez-faire relates to students' academic performance in public secondary schools.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1 There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on the extent authoritarian child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Table 5: t-test Analysis of significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on the extent authoritarian child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students

Variables/Status	No. of Respondents	\bar{X}	SD	DF	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male Teachers	150	3.19	0.77	398	1.20	1.96	Accepted
Female Teachers	250	3.29	0.72				

Significant $P < 0.005$

Analysis on table 4.5 reveals that the t-cal (1.20) is less than the t-crit (1.96). Therefore, the calculated ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is smaller than the given critical value of ratio. So, the hypothesis 1 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that there is no significant

difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on the extent authoritarian child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on the extent permissive child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 6: t-test Analysis of significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on the extent permissive child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students

Variables/Status	No. of Respondents	\bar{X}	SD	DF	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male Teachers	150	2.67	0.84	398	0.52	1.96	Accepted
Female Teachers	250	3.22	0.74				

Significant P<0.005

Analysis on table 6 indicates that the t-cal (0.52) is less than the t-crit (1.96). So, the calculated t-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is less than the given critical value of t-ratio. Therefore, the hypothesis 2 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on the extent permissive child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on the extent authoritative child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 7: t-test Analysis of significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on the extent authoritative child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students

Variables/Status	No. of Respondents	\bar{X}	SD	DF	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male Teachers	150	3.22	0.77	398	0.48	1.96	Accepted
Female Teachers	250	3.19	0.77				

Significant P<0.005

Analysis on table 7 shows that the t-cal (0.49) is less than the t-crit (1.96). So, the calculated t-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significant since it is less than the given critical value of ratio. Therefore, the hypothesis 3 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on the extent authoritative child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on the extent uninvolved child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 8: t-test Analysis of significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on the extent uninvolved child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students

Variables/Status	No. of Respondents	\bar{X}	SD	DF	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male Teachers	150	2.93	0.76	398	1.20	1.96	Accepted
Female Teachers	250	3.27	0.74				

Significant P<0.005

Analysis on table 8 reveals that the t-cal (1.20) is less than the t-crit (1.96). Therefore, the calculated ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is smaller than the given critical value of ratio. So, the hypothesis 4 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on the extent uninvolved child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study in research question one: To what extent does authoritarian child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis revealed that authoritarian child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. This view is in collaboration with Conger and Galanbos (2017) who observed that some parental way of life imposes restrictions which affect the child's study habit in secondary school. They also accepted the point that parents in autocratic child rearing pattern are responsive to their children's needs and their point of view. It was also observed from the reveal that the respondents accepted the fact that strict rules are given and enforced by parents in autocratic child rearing pattern which may affect the students' study habit. The analysis also indicates that the respondents accepted that children from autocratic parenting family are obedient, conforming and academic competent. It still shows that the respondents accepted that being fearful, irritable, easily annoyed, passively hostile is some of the qualities of autocratic parenting style.

The study in research question two: To what extent does permissive child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis indicated that permissive child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. This was supported with the view of Bakker (2019) who asserts that parents not having adequate control or regulation of their children affect their study habits. The analysis also shows that the respondents accepted the point that children from permissive parental home exhibit worse impulse control thereby affecting their study habits. It was still observed from the study that the respondents accepted the fact that children from permissive parental home have more behavioural problem which affect their study habits. The respondents also accepted the view that democratic parenting styles relate to students' study habits in secondary schools. The analysis still reveals that the respondents accepted the point that children from permissive parental home have low motivation thereby affecting their study habits.

The findings of the study in research question three: To what extent does authoritative child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis showed that authoritative child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. This view was supported by Ezewu (2013) who admitted that authoritative parenting style promotes students study habits in secondary school. The analysis also indicates that the respondents accepted the point that authoritative parenting style promotes students' self-efficacy thereby enhancing their study habits. It was still observed from the study that the respondents accepted the view that students from authoritative parenting home have mastery goal behaviour like independence which enhance their study habits. The analysis still shows that the respondents accepted the fact that authoritative parenting style raised the confidence of their children thereby enhancing their study habits. The study also shows that the respondents accepted the point that better social styles and pitiable problem –solving enhance students study habits.

The study in research question four: To what extent does uninvolved child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis revealed that uninvolved child rearing techniques affects the academic performance of students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. This was supported with the view of Bakker (2019) who asserts that parents having minimum interference in their children affect their study habits. They also accepted the point that Parental practice of allowing children to act or behave how they want affects their study habits. It was also observed from the study that the respondents accepted the fact that parental little or no inter reference or regulation affect their study habits. The analysis also indicates that the respondents accepted that laissez-faire parental pattern leads to the lowest

productivity among the students. It still shows that the respondents accepted that laissez-faire relates to students' study habits in public secondary schools.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it was therefore deduced that parenting lifestyle like authoritarian pattern of child rearing, permissive pattern of child rearing, authoritative pattern of child rearing and Laissez-faire pattern of child rearing relate significantly to secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State. The study also deduced that good parenting lifestyle helps to improve academic ability of standard of the children.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are thereby put forward to ensure that there is a good relationship between or among child rearing patterns or styles and study habits of secondary school students in Rivers State.

1. Government should organize awareness campaign on the right parenting style or pattern to use
2. Parents should keep the right relationship with their family for their children upbringing
3. Government should organize awareness campaign on the roles of authoritative pattern of child rearing to the parents
4. Parents should avoid laissez-faire type of parenting style hence it affects the students negatively.

REFERENCES

- Amajirionwu, S.A. (2021). *Attitude towards rearing up Nigerian children*. AICE, Owerri: Unpublished Research Project.
- Baumrind, D. (2021). Current patterns of parental authority. *Development Psychology Monograph*. 4th ed. Lagos: Nigeria.
- Baumrind, D. (2016). Authoritarian Vs. authoritative parental control. *Adolescence*, 3, 255-272.
- Bissell, M. (2020). Socio-economic outcomes of teenage pregnancy and parenthood: A review of the literature. *The Canadian Journal of Human Sexuality*, 9, 192-204.
- Blum, R. (2016). Youth in Sub-Sahara Africa. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 4(1), 230-238.
- Carmen, S.F. (2016). *Teenage pregnancy prevention: Statistics and programs congressional research service*.
- Carrera, M.A. (2022). Sign of the times. *The Guardian, Sunday*, 15 (39), 27.
- Cater, S. & Coleman, L. (2016). *Planned teenage pregnancy, perspectives of young parents from disadvantaged backgrounds*. Bristol: Joseph Rown Free Foundation.
- Child, D. (2018). *Psychology and the teacher (second edition)*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston Inc.
- Cole, L. & Hall, I.H. (2020). *Psychology of adolescence (seventh edition)*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston Inc.
- Dangal, G. (2016). Teenage pregnancy: Complexities and challenges. *Journal of the Nepal Medical Association*, 45(5), 262-272.
- Dressier, D. & Carns, D. (2013). *Sociology and study of human interaction*. New York: Alfred A. Knopf Inc.
- Erickson, S. (2018). *Teenage pregnancy prevention: Statistics and programmes congressional research service*. Ibadan: Psychoeducational Productions.
- Ezewu, E. (2013). *Sociology of education (2nd impression)*. Lagos: Longman Nigeria Limited.
- Gardner, W. I. (2018). *Children with learning and behaviour problems*. London: Allyn and Bacon inc.
- Grasha, L. (2015). *Planned teenage pregnancy: Perspectives of young parents from disadvantaged backgrounds*. Bristol: Joseph Rown Free Foundation.
- Iwundu, C. (2015). *An outline of educational psychology. Child's development and learning*. AICE Owerri: Unpublished Monograph.

- Kemjika, O.G. (2018). Relationship between study habits and student achievement among secondary school students in Rivers State. *Nigerian Journal of Professional Studies*.
- Mac-Adam, R. (2014). Family variation in storm and stress. *Journal of Adolescent Research*, 1, 15-31.
- Miller, B.C. (2020). Family influence on adolescent sexual and contraceptive. *Journal of Research*, 39 (17), 2.
- Nei, A.S. (2013). *A radical approach to child rearing*. New York: Macmillan Publisher Limited.
- Ogori, S.A. & Yuruba, A.R. (2013). The cause and effect of pregnancy. international open. *Journal of Educational Research*, Vol. 1, No.7.
- Oko, I. (2019). The intra-cultural comparison of traditional and modern child rearing practices in the formation of achievement motives. A term paper presented in the Faculty of Management Science, University of Port Harcourt.
- Okwubunka, S. (2013). *Career strategies for youths*. Makurdi: Onaiva Printing and Publishing Co. Ltd.
- Onomuodeke, M.A. (2018). An Investigation into some correlates of study habits of secondary school students in Benin City, Bendel State. Unpublished Masters Degree Dissertation, University of Benin.
- Onyejiaku, F.C. (2017). *Techniques of effective study: A manual for students in schools Colleges and Universities*. Calabar: Nusen Press Ltd.
- Peretomode, B. (2013). Process evaluation of the teacher training for an AIDS prevention programme. *Health Education Research*, 21(2), 621-633.
- Procter, C.G.M. (2016). *Study habit inventory and manual*. Ibadan. *Psychoeducational Productions* 30(11), 77-79.
- Sagem, A.M. & Nury, A.T.M. (2011). *Factors associated with teenage marital pregnancy among Bangladeshi women*.
- Shafter, E.B. (2018). *Introduction of psychology (3rd edition)*. New York: Harcourt Brace & World Inc.
- Uba, A. (2017). *The psychoanalytic approach of Sigmund Freud*. In A. Uba (Ed). *Theories of personality*. Ibadan: Clareriaum Press, 1-21.
- Weiss, L.H. & Schwatz, J.C. (2011). The relationship between parenting types and older adolescents' personality, academic achievement and substance use. *Child Development*, 65, 5.